

SEISMEC

NEWSWAVE

Dear reader,

Welcome to our first official newsletter!

We are excited to bring you the latest updates and insights from the SEISMEC project. In this inaugural issue, we will introduce you to SEISMEC's vision, core ideas and objectives, as well as provide an overview of our most recent accomplishments, project highlights and a sneak peek of what's coming next. Jump in, fasten your seatbelts and get ready to pilot the shift towards a human-centric industry!

SEISMEC in a nutshell

SEISMEC demonstrates the concept of human-centricity across a wide array of industrial sectors, scales and sociotechnical contexts in the EU. By effectively empowering workers in the co-design and co-development of new technologies, we facilitate the journey towards a skills-driven and creativity-infused industrial landscape; one that is built around high-quality, sustainable jobs, and prioritises overall worker security and satisfaction.

[LEARN MORE](#)

The start of our 4-year journey

SEISMEC's kick-off meeting was held in Rotterdam last February, under the wonderful hosting of our coordinators, Erasmus University Rotterdam. The two-day event began with a "Better Work, Better Workplaces" mini-symposium and continued the next day with in-depth project discussions!

OUR STORY

Get to know us - The dream team

It all started when a team of key players in the EU industrial and academic landscape put their heads together to focus on human-centrism, worker empowerment and how to guide the transition to a more resilient Industry 5.0. SEISMEC unites cutting-edge engineering, computer science and networking under the inquiring lens of social sciences and humanities.

MEET THE TEAM

All about CAPS

How can industries ensure that technology empowers workers while enhancing competitiveness? Our CAPS framework can help strike a balance between key concepts of Creativity and Collaboration, Autonomy and Automation, Privacy and Productivity, Safety and Satisfaction. Visit our brand-new CAPS self-assessment and explore these concepts from multiple perspectives to see where you stand in your organisation!

CHECK IT OUT

SEISMEC at CESI Summer Days

Our partner CESI successfully hosted their Summer Days 2024 and SEISMEC was there! The event examined the intersection of new technologies, AI and gender equality in the workplace. Colleagues Jason Pridmore and Selma Toktas contributed with a talk on "Equitable AI: Addressing bias in employment opportunities". Take a look at the official video recap of the event!

[REVISIT THE EVENT](#)

SEISMEC's reading corner

From 4.0 to 5.0: setting human-centricity at the core of the next industrial revolution. Are you curious to learn how humanity has reached the foothills of Industry 5.0? Check out our blog "From the industrial to the human-centric revolution: Transitioning from an industry-focused society to one centered around humanity" and time-travel with us through all previous industrial revolutions.

[READ MORE](#)

Funded by the
European Union

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 101135884. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them..